

STUDY PROTOCOL

Physiological responses to manual therapy in healthy humans: an experimental study on the relationship between applied pressure, manual technique, and autonomic, hormonal, and vascular responses. A randomized clinical trial.

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Principal investigator

Vanesa Abuín-Porras, PhD

Universidad Europea de Madrid, Faculty of Medicine, Health and Sports, Department of Physiotherapy, Campus de Villaviciosa, Calle Tajo s/n 28670, Villaviciosa de Odón, Madrid, Spain. STRONG Research Group, Universidad Europea de Madrid, Villaviciosa de Odón, Madrid, Spain. ORCID: 0000-0002-1782-2524

Email: vanesa.abuin@universidadeuropea.es

Research team

Elena Velarde-Fernández

Raquel Pérez-García

Álvaro Macías-Martínez

Isabel Mínguez Esteban

Affiliations

Universidad Europea de Madrid, Faculty of Medicine, Health and Sports, Department of Physiotherapy, Campus de Villaviciosa, Calle Tajo s/n 28670, Villaviciosa de Odón, Madrid, Spain.

Study site

Universidad Europea de Madrid

Sponsor

Colegio Profesional de Fisioterapeutas de la Comunidad de Madrid

Ethics approval

This protocol has been approved by the **Research Ethics Committee of Hospita Clínico San Carlos** approval code **26/049-E**, on **February 2026**

Study registration

ClinicalTrials.gov

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Keywords

Manual therapy; massage therapy; oncology massage; manual lymphatic drainage; deep tissue massage; pressure dosage; clinical safety; autonomic response; heart rate variability; cortisol; VEGF; IL-6; Doppler ultrasound; crossover study.

Structured abstract

Background: Manual therapy techniques are widely used in physiotherapy and other healthcare settings, including in populations with increased clinical vulnerability such as people living with or beyond cancer. However, the physiological safety profile of manual therapy protocols involving different levels of pressure remains insufficiently characterized. In particular, there is limited evidence on whether graded manual pressure induces differential acute autonomic, hormonal, immune, sensory, and vascular responses under controlled experimental conditions.

Objective: The primary objective of this study is to characterize and compare the acute autonomic, immune, and vascular physiological responses induced by three manual therapy protocols involving different pressure intensities: manual lymphatic drainage, oncology massage, and decontracting massage, in healthy adults.

Design: This is a prospective, analytical, randomized crossover experimental study with a within-subject design. Each participant will receive the three manual therapy protocols in separate experimental sessions, in a randomized order, acting as their own control.

Participants: Healthy adults aged 18 to 65 years will be recruited from the general population linked to the study site. Participants will be eligible if they have no relevant musculoskeletal, neurological, or cardiovascular condition and no clinically significant cervical or shoulder girdle pain. Individuals with contraindications to manual therapy, conditions or medication that may substantially alter autonomic, hormonal, cardiovascular, or immune responses, pregnancy, or any condition that may compromise participant safety or data validity will be excluded.

Interventions: Participants will receive three manual therapy protocols in independent sessions separated by a minimum washout interval: manual lymphatic drainage, oncology massage, and decontracting massage. The protocols represent increasing levels of manual pressure and will be standardized in terms of pressure range, application pattern, and duration. Applied pressure will be objectively monitored during the intervention.

Outcomes: The study will assess autonomic responses, including heart rate, heart rate variability, skin temperature, galvanic skin response, and blood pressure. Sensory outcomes will include mechanical pain threshold assessed with von Frey filaments. Hormonal and immune outcomes will include capillary blood levels of cortisol, vascular endothelial growth factor, interleukin-6, and leukocyte subpopulations. Vascular outcomes will be assessed by B-mode and Doppler ultrasound of the left common carotid artery, including luminal diameter, intima-media thickness, and peak systolic velocity. Body composition will be assessed by dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry, and subjective perception of massage intensity and effects will be recorded after each session.

Sample size: Based on repeated-measures analysis for within-subject comparisons and using heart rate variability as the reference outcome, a minimum sample size of 20 participants was estimated. To account for potential losses, 25 participants will be recruited, resulting in 75 experimental sessions.

Statistical analysis: Descriptive analyses will be performed for all variables. The main analysis will use linear mixed models including manual therapy protocol as a fixed effect, participant as a random effect, and order/session as a covariate. Repeated-measures analyses will be used for pre-post comparisons within each experimental session. Normality will be assessed, and non-parametric alternatives will be applied when appropriate. The significance level will be set at $\alpha = 0.05$.

Ethics and dissemination: The study has received ethics approval from the relevant Research Ethics Committee. All participants will provide written informed consent before enrolment. Results will be disseminated through peer-reviewed publications, scientific conferences, and professional knowledge-transfer activities.

Trial registration: ClinicalTrials.gov, NCT07393815.

Keywords: manual therapy; manual lymphatic drainage; oncology massage; decontracting massage; pressure dosage; autonomic response; heart rate variability; cortisol; VEGF; IL-6; Doppler ultrasound; crossover study.

1. Introduction

Manual therapy techniques are widely used in physiotherapy and other healthcare settings for the management of pain, tissue mobility, swelling, muscle tension, and perceived relaxation. These interventions include a broad range of techniques that differ in their therapeutic intention, mechanical characteristics, pressure intensity, rhythm, depth, and target tissues. Despite their extensive clinical use, the physiological effects induced by different manual therapy protocols remain incompletely understood, particularly when the intervention is considered not only in terms of clinical effectiveness but also in terms of physiological safety and dosage.

Previous research has suggested that manual therapy may induce acute changes in autonomic nervous system activity, pain perception, hormonal regulation, and tissue-related responses. However, the available evidence remains heterogeneous, partly because manual therapy interventions are often insufficiently standardized. One of the main methodological limitations in this field is the lack of objective monitoring of the pressure applied during treatment. As a result, commonly used descriptors such as “light”, “moderate”, or “deep” pressure are frequently based on therapist perception or clinical tradition rather than on quantified mechanical parameters. This limits reproducibility, hinders comparisons across studies, and restricts the development of evidence-based criteria for safe and individualized dosage.

This limitation is particularly relevant in clinically vulnerable populations, such as people living with or beyond cancer. In oncology-related care, manual lymphatic drainage and light-pressure massage protocols are commonly used because of their perceived safety and tolerability. At the same time, more intense manual therapy approaches may be avoided in these populations due to precautionary concerns regarding tissue fragility, vascular response, immune function, or disease-related vulnerability. However, these restrictions are not always supported by direct physiological evidence. A better understanding of the acute physiological responses induced by graded manual pressure may therefore contribute to more informed clinical decision-making and to the safe integration of manual therapy in complex clinical contexts.

The present study addresses this gap by comparing three standardized manual therapy protocols that represent increasing levels of pressure intensity: manual lymphatic drainage, oncology massage, and decontracting massage. These interventions differ not only in pressure magnitude but also in rhythm, depth, speed, and clinical purpose. By applying all three protocols to the same participants in a randomized crossover design, the study aims to reduce inter-individual variability and to characterize protocol-specific physiological responses under controlled experimental conditions.

A distinctive feature of this protocol is the integration of multiple physiological domains within a single experimental framework. Autonomic responses will be assessed through heart rate, heart rate variability, skin temperature, galvanic skin response, and blood pressure. Sensory responses will be evaluated through mechanical pain threshold. Hormonal and immune responses will be explored through capillary blood markers, including cortisol, vascular endothelial growth factor, interleukin-6, and leukocyte subpopulations. In addition, vascular responses will be assessed by B-mode and Doppler ultrasound of the left common carotid artery. Body composition will also be measured to explore whether baseline adiposity and lean mass are associated with sensory responses to manual pressure.

This experimental approach is intended to provide a controlled physiological model for understanding the immediate effects and safety profile of graded manual pressure in healthy adults. Although the study is not designed to establish clinical efficacy in patients, its findings may provide a relevant translational basis for future clinical studies in oncology and other vulnerable populations. By objectively monitoring both the pressure applied and the physiological responses elicited, the study aims to contribute to the standardization, personalization, and safer clinical use of manual therapy techniques.

2. Objectives and hypotheses

2.1. Primary objective

The primary objective of this study is to characterize and compare the acute autonomic, immune, and vascular physiological responses induced by three standardized manual therapy protocols involving different pressure intensities: manual lymphatic drainage, oncology massage, and decontracting massage, in healthy adults.

2.2. Secondary objectives

The secondary objectives are:

1. To analyse the autonomic responses associated with each manual therapy protocol, including heart rate, heart rate variability, skin temperature, galvanic skin response, and systolic and diastolic blood pressure.
2. To evaluate acute changes in mechanical pain threshold after each manual therapy protocol, assessed with von Frey filaments at predefined anatomical sites.
3. To determine changes in capillary blood cortisol levels associated with each manual therapy protocol and to compare these changes between the three techniques.
4. To analyse immune responses associated with each manual therapy protocol through leukocyte subpopulation counts and capillary blood interleukin-6 levels.
5. To assess capillary blood levels of vascular endothelial growth factor before and after each experimental session and to compare the acute changes between the three manual therapy protocols.
6. To characterize acute vascular changes in the left common carotid artery using B-mode and Doppler ultrasound, including luminal diameter, intima–media thickness, and peak systolic velocity.
7. To explore the association between baseline body composition, assessed by dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry, and mechanical pain threshold responses according to the manual therapy protocol applied.
8. To analyse the relationship between objective physiological changes and participants' subjective perception of massage intensity, comfort, tolerance, and global perceived effect after each intervention.

2.3. Study hypothesis

The study hypothesis is that standardized manual therapy protocols involving different pressure intensities will induce differentiated acute physiological responses in healthy adults. Specifically, manual lymphatic drainage, oncology massage, and decontracting massage are expected to produce distinct autonomic, immune, hormonal, sensory, and vascular response profiles. It is further hypothesized that objective monitoring of the applied pressure and the associated physiological responses will allow the identification of protocol-specific safety profiles. This information may contribute to improving pressure dosage, standardization, and individualized clinical decision-making in manual therapy, particularly as a basis for future studies in clinically vulnerable populations.

3. Methods

3.1. Study design

This is a prospective, analytical, randomized crossover experimental study with a within-subject design. Each participant will act as their own control and will receive three standardized manual therapy protocols in separate experimental sessions: manual lymphatic drainage, oncology massage, and decontracting massage. The order of the interventions will be randomized. The crossover design has been selected to reduce inter-individual variability in physiological responses and to allow direct within-participant comparisons between manual therapy protocols involving different pressure intensities. This design is particularly appropriate for the assessment of acute physiological responses under controlled experimental conditions.

Each experimental session will include baseline assessment, application of one manual therapy protocol, continuous recording of autonomic and physiological variables during the intervention, and post-intervention assessment of sensory, hormonal, immune, vascular, and subjective outcomes. The three sessions will be separated by a minimum washout interval of 24 hours.

Due to the nature of the interventions, blinding of the therapist and participants to the intervention received will not be feasible. However, the researchers responsible for physiological data collection and data analysis will remain blinded to the manual therapy protocol applied whenever possible. Data will be coded to prevent identification of the intervention sequence during statistical analysis.

3.2. Study setting

The study will be conducted in the research laboratories of Universidad Europea de Madrid under standardized environmental conditions. Room temperature will be monitored and recorded during each experimental session, as environmental conditions may influence autonomic and vascular measurements.

All assessments and interventions will be performed by trained members of the research team. Manual therapy protocols will be delivered by physiotherapists with specific training in the procedures under investigation. Biological sample collection, physiological monitoring, and ultrasound assessments will be conducted by qualified personnel according to standardized operating procedures.

3.3. Study population

The study population will consist of healthy adults recruited from the general population linked to the study site. Participants will be screened to ensure that they meet the eligibility criteria and that participation is safe and appropriate.

The study will include adult volunteers aged 18 to 65 years with no relevant musculoskeletal, neurological, cardiovascular, or systemic condition that could interfere with the intervention or with the interpretation of physiological outcomes.

3.4. Eligibility criteria

Inclusion criteria

Participants will be eligible if they meet all of the following criteria:

1. Age between 18 and 65 years.
2. No known relevant musculoskeletal, neurological, cardiovascular, or systemic disease.
3. No clinically significant musculoskeletal pain in the cervical region, shoulder region, or shoulder girdle at the time of inclusion.
4. Ability to understand the study information and follow the study procedures.
5. Provision of written informed consent before any study-related procedure.

Exclusion criteria

Participants will be excluded if they meet any of the following criteria:

1. Any medical contraindication to manual therapy.
2. Acute or chronic musculoskeletal disorder affecting the cervical region, shoulder region, or shoulder girdle that may interfere with the intervention.

3. Use of medication that may substantially alter autonomic, hormonal, cardiovascular, inflammatory, or immune responses.
4. Relevant cardiovascular disease, including uncontrolled hypertension, significant arrhythmia, previous myocardial infarction, or other conditions judged clinically relevant by the research team.
5. Neurological disease affecting sensitivity, autonomic regulation, or cardiovascular control.
6. Coagulation disorders or use of high-dose anticoagulant treatment.
7. Pregnancy or suspected pregnancy.
8. Any condition that, in the opinion of the principal investigator, may compromise participant safety or interfere with the validity of the data collected.

3.5. Withdrawal criteria

Participants may be withdrawn from the study if they request withdrawal at any time, if they develop any condition meeting the exclusion criteria during the study, if an adverse event occurs that makes continuation inadvisable, or if the research team identifies any circumstance that may compromise participant safety or data validity.

Participants who withdraw from the study will be asked whether the data collected up to the time of withdrawal may be retained for analysis. No further data will be collected after withdrawal of consent.

3.6. Interventions

Each participant will receive three standardized manual therapy protocols in separate experimental sessions: manual lymphatic drainage, oncology massage, and decontracting massage. These protocols have been selected because they represent different levels of manual pressure and different clinical application patterns within physiotherapy practice.

The interventions will be applied in a randomized order. Each participant will therefore complete three experimental sessions, receiving only one manual therapy protocol per session. The sessions will be separated by a minimum washout interval of 24 hours to reduce the potential influence of acute carryover effects between interventions.

All manual therapy procedures will be performed by trained physiotherapists following standardized instructions regarding anatomical region, pressure range, rhythm, speed, duration, and participant positioning. Applied pressure will be objectively monitored during each intervention using pressure sensors placed on the therapist's hand. This will allow continuous recording of the mechanical stimulus delivered during each manual therapy protocol.

3.6.1. Manual lymphatic drainage

Manual lymphatic drainage will be applied using basic manoeuvres based on the Vodder method. This protocol will involve gentle, rhythmic, superficial manual techniques intended to stimulate lymphatic flow while minimizing mechanical tissue load.

The target pressure will be approximately 40 mmHg, with a rhythm consistent with the physiological contraction pattern of the lymphangion. The approximate duration of the intervention will be 40 minutes. The therapist will maintain a slow and controlled rhythm throughout the intervention, avoiding painful pressure or excessive tissue compression.

3.6.2. Oncology massage

The oncology massage protocol will consist of light-pressure massage manoeuvres adapted to a low mechanical load. This intervention is intended to represent a gentle massage approach commonly used in clinically vulnerable populations, including people living with or beyond cancer. The pressure range will be between 0.5 and 0.8 N/cm². The approximate speed of application will be 5 cm/s, consistent with superficial and rhythmic manual manoeuvres. The duration of the intervention will be between 20 and 30 minutes. The therapist will avoid deep pressure, abrupt changes in rhythm, or any manoeuvre that causes discomfort to the participant.

3.6.3. Decontracting massage

The decontracting massage protocol will consist of moderate-pressure manual techniques commonly used in musculoskeletal physiotherapy to reduce muscle tension and improve soft tissue extensibility.

The pressure range will be between 2 and 3 N/cm². The speed of application will range between 1 and 5 cm/s, according to the standardized sequence of the intervention. The approximate duration of the intervention will be 20 minutes. Although this protocol involves higher pressure than the other two interventions, pressure will remain within the predefined safety range and will not exceed the participant's tolerance.

3.7. General experimental procedure

Each experimental session will follow the same structure. On arrival, participants will rest under standardized environmental conditions before baseline measurements are obtained. Room temperature will be recorded. The participant will then undergo baseline assessment of autonomic, sensory, hormonal, immune, and vascular variables according to the predefined measurement schedule.

During the intervention, heart rate, heart rate variability, skin temperature, and galvanic skin response will be recorded continuously. Blood pressure will be assessed according to the study protocol. Applied manual pressure will be continuously monitored using the pressure recording system.

Immediately after each intervention, post-intervention measurements will be obtained. These will include mechanical pain threshold, blood pressure, capillary blood sampling for biochemical and immune markers, and subjective perception of the intervention. Doppler ultrasound assessment of the left common carotid artery will be performed before the intervention and ten minutes after the experimental session.

Body composition will be assessed in an independent visit using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry. This assessment will include total and segmental body fat percentage and total and segmental lean mass.

3.8. Safety and stopping criteria during the intervention

Participants will be monitored throughout each experimental session. The intervention will be interrupted if the participant reports excessive pain, dizziness, nausea, discomfort, anxiety, or any other symptom that makes continuation inadvisable. The intervention may also be stopped at the discretion of the research team if any physiological response is considered clinically inappropriate or potentially unsafe.

Participants will be reminded that they may request interruption or withdrawal from the session at any time, without providing a reason and without any negative consequence.

3.9. Outcomes

The study will include autonomic, sensory, hormonal, immune, vascular, body composition, and subjective perception outcomes. All variables will be collected according to standardized procedures and predefined time points.

3.9.1. Autonomic and physiological outcomes

Autonomic and physiological responses will be assessed during each experimental session using the following variables:

- Heart rate, expressed in beats per minute.
- Heart rate variability, expressed in milliseconds and derived from continuous heart rate recording.
- Skin temperature, expressed in degrees Celsius.
- Galvanic skin response, expressed in microsiemens.
- Systolic and diastolic blood pressure, expressed in mmHg.

Heart rate and heart rate variability will be continuously recorded using a validated chest strap device. Skin temperature will be recorded using a superficial temperature probe. Galvanic skin response will be recorded using surface electrodes placed on the non-dominant hand. Blood pressure will be measured by trained personnel using a manual sphygmomanometer.

3.9.2. Sensory outcome

Mechanical pain threshold will be assessed using von Frey filaments. Measurements will be performed at predefined anatomical sites, including the ipsilateral and contralateral trapezius region and the ipsilateral and contralateral proximal anteromedial forearm.

Mechanical pain threshold will be expressed in grams and calculated using the up-down method based on the XO algorithm.

3.9.3. Hormonal outcomes

Hormonal response will be assessed using capillary blood samples collected before and after each intervention. The following marker will be analysed:

- Cortisol concentration, expressed in $\mu\text{g/dL}$.

Cortisol will be determined using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay kits.

3.9.4. Immune and inflammatory outcomes

Immune and inflammatory responses will be assessed using capillary blood samples collected before and after each intervention. The following variables will be analysed:

- Leukocyte subpopulation count, expressed as cells/ μL .
- Interleukin-6 concentration, expressed in pg/mL .

Leukocyte subpopulations will be analysed using a point-of-care haematological analyser.

Interleukin-6 will be determined using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay kits.

3.9.5. Vascular outcomes

Vascular responses will be assessed using B-mode and Doppler ultrasound of the left common carotid artery. The following variables will be obtained:

- Luminal diameter, expressed in mm.
- Intima-media thickness, expressed in mm.
- Peak systolic velocity, expressed in cm/s .
- Absolute and relative change in luminal diameter between baseline and post-intervention assessment.

Ultrasound assessment will be performed with the participant in supine position, with the backrest reclined at 30° , the head rotated 45° to the right, and cervical extension controlled using a support under the neck. Measurements will be performed before the intervention and ten minutes after the experimental session.

3.9.6. Vascular endothelial growth factor

Capillary blood levels of vascular endothelial growth factor will be assessed before and after each intervention and expressed in pg/mL . Vascular endothelial growth factor will be determined using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay kits.

3.9.7. Body composition

Body composition will be assessed in an independent visit using dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry. The following variables will be obtained:

- Total body fat percentage.
- Segmental body fat percentage.
- Total lean mass, expressed in kg.
- Segmental lean mass, expressed in kg.

These variables will be used to explore whether baseline body composition is associated with mechanical pain threshold and physiological responses to manual pressure.

3.9.8. Subjective perception after the intervention

After each experimental session, participants will complete a post-intervention questionnaire assessing their subjective perception of the manual therapy protocol. The questionnaire will include perceived pressure intensity, comfort, tolerance, and global perceived effect of the massage. Responses will be recorded using ordinal Likert-type scales.

3.10. Measurement schedule

The measurement schedule will be structured as follows:

Baseline assessment before each session:

Blood pressure, mechanical pain threshold, capillary blood sample, and ultrasound assessment of the left common carotid artery will be obtained before the application of the assigned manual therapy protocol.

Continuous recording during each session:

Heart rate, heart rate variability, skin temperature, galvanic skin response, and applied manual pressure will be recorded continuously throughout the intervention.

Immediate post-intervention assessment:

Blood pressure, mechanical pain threshold, capillary blood sample, and subjective perception of the intervention will be collected immediately after the intervention.

Delayed post-intervention assessment:

Ultrasound assessment of the left common carotid artery will be repeated ten minutes after the experimental session.

Independent body composition assessment:

Dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry will be performed in a separate visit to assess total and segmental body composition.

3.11. Sample size

The sample size was estimated using G*Power 3.1.9.7. The calculation was based on within-subject repeated-measures comparisons, using heart rate variability as the reference physiological outcome. Specifically, the root mean square of successive differences was selected because of its sensitivity to short-term parasympathetic modulation and its relevance for the assessment of acute autonomic responses during manual therapy interventions.

Given the variability reported in previous studies evaluating acute heart rate variability responses to manual therapy, a conservative effect size was assumed. The calculation was performed for an F test, using repeated-measures analysis within factors, with one group and three repeated measurements corresponding to the three manual therapy protocols. The following parameters were used: effect size $f = 0.30$, alpha level = 0.05, statistical power = 80%, expected correlation among repeated measures = 0.50, and nonsphericity correction $\epsilon = 1$.

Under these assumptions, the minimum required sample size was 20 participants. To account for potential dropouts or incomplete experimental sessions, 25 participants will be recruited. Since each participant will complete three experimental sessions, the study will include a total of 75 intervention sessions.

3.12. Randomization and allocation sequence

The order in which each participant receives the three manual therapy protocols will be randomized. The randomization sequence will be generated by a researcher who is not involved in the application of the interventions.

A simple randomization procedure will be used to determine the sequence of the three interventions for each participant. The allocation sequence will be generated using Epidat 4.2 and will be kept in opaque, sealed envelopes until the corresponding experimental session.

Each participant will receive all three interventions, but the order of administration will vary according to the randomized sequence. This procedure is intended to minimize order effects and to reduce the potential influence of systematic sequence bias.

3.13. Blinding

Due to the nature of the manual therapy interventions, blinding of the therapist applying the techniques will not be feasible. Participants will also not be fully blinded to the intervention received, as the three protocols differ in pressure intensity, rhythm, and perceived mechanical load.

However, researchers responsible for physiological data collection will remain blinded to the intervention sequence whenever possible. Data will be coded before statistical analysis so that the researcher performing the analysis cannot identify the specific intervention or order corresponding to each dataset.

The use of objective physiological, biochemical, sensory, and vascular measurements is expected to reduce the influence of expectation bias on the primary outcomes.

3.14. Data management

All participants will be assigned a numerical study code. This code will be used in all databases, data collection forms, biological sample labels, and statistical analyses. The document linking participant identity to the study code will be stored separately from the research database and will be accessible only to the principal investigator or an authorized member of the research team. Data will be entered into a password-protected electronic database. Range checks and consistency checks will be performed during data entry and data cleaning. Any inconsistencies or missing values will be reviewed against the original data collection forms whenever possible.

Personal data will be processed in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation, and Spanish Organic Law 3/2018 on Personal Data Protection and guarantee of digital rights. Only pseudonymized data will be used for analysis and dissemination. Biological samples obtained from capillary blood will be used exclusively for the analyses specified in this protocol. Samples will not be stored in a biobank and will be destroyed after completion of the planned analyses.

3.15. Data availability

The final anonymized dataset may be made available upon reasonable request, subject to ethical and legal restrictions related to participant confidentiality and data protection. If the dataset is deposited in an open repository, it will be fully anonymized and accompanied by the corresponding data dictionary.

The study protocol will be deposited in Zenodo and assigned a persistent digital object identifier. Any subsequent substantial amendments to the protocol will be documented as a new version.

3.16. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis will be performed using IBM SPSS Statistics, version 29.0, or equivalent validated statistical software. All analyses will be conducted according to a predefined statistical analysis plan before database lock.

Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize participant characteristics and study variables. Quantitative variables will be described as mean and standard deviation when normally distributed, and as median and interquartile range when distributional assumptions are not met. Qualitative variables will be described as absolute and relative frequencies.

The normality of continuous variables will be assessed using the Shapiro–Wilk test, together with visual inspection of histograms, Q–Q plots, and distributional characteristics. Homogeneity of variances and model assumptions will be evaluated where applicable.

The primary analysis will assess differences between the three manual therapy protocols in acute physiological responses. Linear mixed-effects models will be used, with manual therapy protocol as a fixed effect and participant as a random effect. Order of intervention and session number will be included as covariates to account for potential sequence or period effects. When baseline and post-intervention values are available, models will include time, protocol, and the protocol-by-time interaction, allowing the comparison of pre-post changes between interventions.

For outcomes measured continuously during the intervention, such as heart rate, heart rate variability, skin temperature, galvanic skin response, and applied pressure, summary parameters will be calculated for each participant and session. These may include mean values, peak values, minimum values, variability indices, and absolute or relative change from baseline, depending on the nature of each variable. These summary measures will then be compared between protocols using mixed-effects models.

For pre-post outcomes, including mechanical pain threshold, blood pressure, capillary blood biomarkers, and vascular ultrasound parameters, within-session changes will be calculated. Absolute changes and relative percentage changes will be reported when clinically or physiologically meaningful. Differences in change scores between manual therapy protocols will be analysed using repeated-measures models or mixed-effects models, depending on the distribution and structure of the data.

If the assumptions required for parametric analyses are not met, appropriate non-parametric alternatives will be applied. For within-subject comparisons across the three interventions, the Friedman test may be used, followed by post hoc pairwise comparisons when appropriate. For paired pre-post comparisons within each intervention, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test may be used. Associations between physiological responses, subjective perception of the intervention, and body composition variables will be explored using Pearson or Spearman correlation coefficients, depending on data distribution. Additional exploratory regression models may be performed to assess whether baseline body composition, sex, age, body mass index, or room temperature are associated with physiological or sensory responses to manual pressure.

Effect sizes will be reported whenever possible. For repeated-measures comparisons, partial eta-squared or equivalent effect size indices will be provided. For pairwise comparisons, mean differences with 95% confidence intervals will be reported. For non-parametric analyses, appropriate rank-based effect sizes will be considered.

The pattern and extent of missing data will be examined. If missing data are scarce and considered to be missing completely at random or missing at random, complete-case analysis will be performed. If the amount or pattern of missing data is considered relevant, appropriate sensitivity analyses or imputation methods will be considered.

The global level of statistical significance will be set at $\alpha = 0.05$. Given the multidimensional and exploratory nature of several secondary outcomes, p-values for secondary and exploratory analyses will be interpreted cautiously, with emphasis on effect sizes, confidence intervals, and consistency across physiological domains rather than on isolated statistical significance.

4. Ethics and dissemination

4.1. Ethics approval

This study will be conducted in accordance with the ethical principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, Good Clinical Practice principles where applicable, and current Spanish and European legislation governing biomedical research, personal data protection, and participant confidentiality.

The study protocol has been reviewed and approved by the Research Ethics Committee of [name of committee], approval code [approval code], on [approval date]. Any substantial amendment to the protocol will be submitted to the Research Ethics Committee for review and approval before implementation.

4.2. Informed consent

All potential participants will receive written and verbal information about the study before enrolment. The participant information sheet will describe the study objectives, procedures, potential risks and discomforts, expected benefits, confidentiality safeguards, voluntary nature of participation, and the right to withdraw at any time.

Written informed consent will be obtained from all participants before any study-related procedure is performed. Participants will be given sufficient time to read the information sheet, ask questions, and decide whether they wish to participate.

Participation in the study will be voluntary. Participants may withdraw their consent at any time without providing a reason and without any negative consequence. If a participant withdraws, no further data will be collected. The participant will be asked whether data collected before withdrawal may be retained for analysis.

4.3. Risks and safety considerations

The expected risks associated with participation are considered mild and transient. Participants may experience temporary discomfort or mild pain related to manual pressure, local sensitivity in the areas assessed for mechanical pain threshold, mild discomfort or a small local haematoma following capillary blood sampling, and minimal exposure to ionizing radiation during dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry.

The ultrasound assessment of the left common carotid artery is non-invasive and does not involve ionizing radiation. The manual therapy protocols will be applied within predefined safety ranges and will be discontinued if the participant reports excessive discomfort, dizziness, nausea, anxiety, pain, or any other symptom that makes continuation inadvisable.

Pregnant participants or those with suspected pregnancy will be excluded because of the use of dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry. Participants with relevant cardiovascular, neurological, musculoskeletal, coagulation-related, or systemic conditions that could compromise safety or interfere with the interpretation of the outcomes will also be excluded.

4.4. Confidentiality and data protection

All personal data will be processed confidentially and in accordance with Regulation (EU) 2016/679, the General Data Protection Regulation, and Spanish Organic Law 3/2018 on Personal Data Protection and guarantee of digital rights.

Each participant will be assigned a numerical study code. This code will be used in the study database, biological sample identification, data analysis, and dissemination of results. The document linking participant identity to the study code will be stored separately from the research database and will be accessible only to the principal investigator or an authorized member of the research team.

Only pseudonymized data will be used for statistical analysis. Results will be reported in aggregate form, and no information that may allow direct identification of individual participants will be disclosed in publications, conference presentations, repositories, or other dissemination activities.

4.5. Biological samples

Capillary blood samples will be collected exclusively for the analyses specified in this protocol, including cortisol, vascular endothelial growth factor, interleukin-6, and leukocyte subpopulation counts. Samples will not be stored for future unspecified research and will not be deposited in a biobank.

Biological samples will be destroyed after completion of the planned laboratory analyses, in accordance with institutional procedures and applicable biosafety regulations.

4.6. Dissemination plan

The findings of this study will be disseminated through peer-reviewed scientific publications, presentations at national and international conferences, and professional knowledge-transfer activities aimed at physiotherapists and other healthcare professionals.

The study protocol will be deposited in Zenodo and assigned a persistent digital object identifier to ensure public accessibility, citability, and version control. Any subsequent substantial changes to the protocol will be documented as a new version.

The results may also be used to develop applied educational and professional materials, including technical summaries, pressure-dosage guidance documents, and training resources for clinicians. All dissemination outputs will present results in aggregate and non-identifiable form.

4.7. Protocol amendments

Any substantial amendment to this protocol will be documented, dated, and justified. Substantial amendments affecting study objectives, eligibility criteria, intervention procedures, outcome measures, safety procedures, data management, or statistical analysis will be submitted to the relevant Research Ethics Committee for review and approval before implementation.

Minor administrative or editorial changes that do not affect participant safety, study conduct, or interpretation of the results will be recorded in the study documentation. When the protocol is deposited in Zenodo, substantial amendments will be made available as a new version of the protocol to ensure transparency, traceability, and version control.

5. Declarations

5.1. Ethics approval and consent to participate

Ethics approval

This protocol has been approved by the **Research Ethics Committee of Hospita Clínico San Carlos** approval code **26/049-E**, on **February 2026**

Study registration

ClinicalTrials.gov

Registration number: NCT07393815

The study will be conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki, Good Clinical Practice principles where applicable, and current Spanish and European legislation on biomedical research, personal data protection, and participant confidentiality.

All participants will receive written and verbal information about the study and will provide written informed consent before any study-related procedure is performed.

5.2. Consent for publication

Not applicable. This protocol does not include individual participant data, images, or any information that could allow direct identification of participants.

5.3. Availability of data and materials

This protocol will be publicly available in Zenodo and will be assigned a persistent digital object identifier. The final anonymized dataset may be made available upon reasonable request, subject to ethical, legal, and data protection restrictions.

5.4. Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests related to this study.

5.5. Funding

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6. Abbreviations

ACC: Common carotid artery

DEXA: Dual-energy X-ray absorptiometry

DLM: Manual lymphatic drainage

ELISA: Enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay

FC: Heart rate

GDPR: General Data Protection Regulation

GSR: Galvanic skin response

HRV: Heart rate variability

IL-6: Interleukin-6

LOPDGDD: Spanish Organic Law on Personal Data Protection and guarantee of digital rights

RMSSD: Root mean square of successive differences

TM: Manual therapy

VEGF: Vascular endothelial growth factor

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